

Deliverable 6.9

White Paper Submitted to Journal

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Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. RESEARCH	4
3. PUBLICATION	4
REFERENCES	6

1. Introduction

The SciRoc project, funded by the EU-H2020 initiative, is supporting the introduction of robots in Smart Cities through European Robotics League (ERL) tournaments. The project began in February 2018 building on the success of previous EU-FP7/H2020 projects: RoCKIn, euRathlon, EuRoC and ROCKEU2. The project will complete in July 2022.

As part of the projects aims, as described in the Grant Agreement, Deliverable 6.9 looks to draft and submit a white paper on ‘Public perceptions and attitudes towards robotics’ for publication in an academic journal.

2. Research

Research into this topic began by preparing a toolkit for investigating public perceptions in robotics in relation to Smart Cities and the European Robotics League.

This main aim of this toolkit is to address whether public perceptions and trust of robotics are affected by considering them in relation to urban environments, smart cities and data collection. This is a gap in the public perceptions literature that has been identified, and which is an important area to understand to ready ourselves for a future where our data is being collected at every turn, and as we interface with robots more and more in our everyday lives. In order to address this, the primary tool used was a semi-structured interview/questionnaire administered in-person at the 2019 Smart City competition in Milton Keynes. Full documentation on this toolkit can be found in Deliverable 6.3.

Feedback from this questionnaire is presented in the ‘Robots and Smart Cities’ chapter. Whilst the objective of this Deliverable was initially to submit a white paper to an academic journal, the SciRoc project was given the opportunity to publish a full chapter on this topic as part of the ‘How Smart Is Your City? Technological Innovation, Ethics and Inclusiveness’ book series. This chapter is therefore presented as our contribution for Deliverable 6.7.

3. Publication

‘How Smart is your City? Technological Innovation, Ethics and Inclusiveness’ forms part of the Intelligent Systems, Control and Automation: Science and Engineering series and aims to:

- Present the concept of smart city in correspondence to a wise and sustainable approach where the well-being of the common citizen whatever their age or physical status is a priority
- Follows a multidisciplinary approach adopting a people-centred, age- gender- and culture-responsive stance to urban development and technological innovation
- Aims to contribute to the definition of urban ecosystems that are driven by the citizens' collective and individual well-being, respecting human rights in a process where no one can “be left behind”^[1].

The Robots and Smart Cities chapter, written by SciRoc Consortium members Matthew Studley (UWE Bristol) and Hannah Little (UWE Bristol), was published as part of this book in October 2020. The chapter looks to address the following:

‘Robots and Smart Cities seem like natural partners. They both gather data and process it, and could provide added value to each other in a variety of ways. In this chapter, we briefly explore some potential use cases featuring the smart city as an informational entity, and a variety of robots. It becomes clear that robots could have an enormous impact on the way that cities are designed and operate and that the closer integration of such ‘autonomous’ machines into our living, working and public spaces will similarly change the way we interact with the city, and with each other. In order to promote public discussion of these impacts, and in the hope that citizens equipped with knowledge are empowered to actively choose the way their environment develops, we introduced the Robots in Smart Cities Challenge to the European Robotics League. This places robots and researchers in the heart of the Smart City, showing skills and technologies in a variety of relatable and believable use cases, or Episodes. The first such challenge was a tremendous success, and we report briefly on the impacts, and feedback gathered from public and other stakeholders as a result.’^[2]

The full chapter can be accessed via: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-56926-6_7

References

- [1] Aldinhas Ferreira, M.I. (2021). *Intelligent Systems, Control and Automation: Science and Engineering* (1). Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56926-6>
- [2] Studley, M.E., Little, H. (2021). Robots in Smart Cities. In: Aldinhas Ferreira, M.I. (Eds.), *How Smart Is Your City?. Intelligent Systems, Control and Automation: Science and Engineering* (pp. 75-88). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56926-6_7